

Synthesis of Certain Schiff Bases Derived from 2-Amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles

S. Giri and H. Singh

Several Schiff bases are known to possess biological activities, like tuberculostatic^{1,2}, fungicidal³, and bacteriostatic⁴. Tibione(I) is a valuable tuberculostat⁵ and sulphathiadiazole is a moderately active antitubercular compound⁵. It was therefore thought of interest to synthesise Schiff bases derived from aminothiadiazoles and aromatic aldehydes. Such compounds may be considered to have the essential features of both thiosemicarbazide and a substituted benzaldehyde(II), connected at the azomethine link, and thus these may have interesting biological properties. Several such compounds prepared are recorded in Table I.

General Method of Preparation.—A mixture of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (0.1M) and an appropriate aldehyde (0.1M) in anhydrous ethanol was refluxed for 3-4 hr. and the solution was filtered. The filtrate on cooling deposited a crystalline product which in most cases required no further purification.

TABLE I
Schiff bases (II).

R ₂ .	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
R ₁ = phenyl.					
H	120-21°	64	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₃ S	15.74	15.94
4-Chloro-	195°	85	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₃ ClS	14.24	14.02
2-Chloro-	132°	82	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₃ ClS	14.48	14.02
4-Bromo-	103°	50	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₃ BrS	14.43	14.87
4-Hydroxy-	100-01°	73	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ON ₃ S	14.06	14.04
2-Hydroxy-	162-63°	73	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ON ₃ S	14.62	14.84
4-Methoxy-	190-92°	45	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₃ S	14.12	14.28

1. Muelin *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, **36**, 886.

2. *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, **52**, 1114, 10206.

3. Farrow *et al.*, *J. Am. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1954, **43**, 370.

4. *Chem. Abs.*, 1952, **46**, 3957.

5. Burger, "Medicinal Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 2nd ed., p. 978

TABLE I (contd.)

R ₁	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
R = 3-nitrophenyl.					
H	108°	71	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ S	18.20	18.06
4-Chloro-	150°	80	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	16.32	16.25
2-Chloro-	185°	80	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	16.12	16.25
4-Fluoro-	150-52°	07	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ FS	17.28	17.07
4-Hydroxy-	250°	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₄ S	18.14	18.07
2-Hydroxy-	177°	71	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₄ S	18.10	18.07
4-Methoxy-	205°	00	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₄ S	16.54	16.47

The authors thank Professor R. P. Rastogi, Head of the Chemistry Department, for providing necessary facilities. One of them (H.S.) is grateful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a junior research fellowship.

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF GORAKHPUR,
GORAKHPUR, U.P.

Received November 22, 1965.